

Physics-Aware Validation of State Estimations for electrical Power Grids based on Artificial Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Distribution system state estimation is increasingly being carried out using artificial neural networks, as these data-driven models enable observability with just a few measurement locations. Despite some clear advantages, a central criticism is the lack of explainability in the results from these deterministic estimates. In this article, estimated nodal voltages obtained from a neural network estimator for a 44-node mixed power grid are evaluated. By relying on the grid's admittances, the predictions provide various combinations of network currents. Knowing where electrical drains and sources are located, allows for the calculation of virtual load impedances. Thus, mesh current analysis offers physically coherent results for possible grid states. A distance analysis classifies the predicted voltages regarding their physical accordance and indicates where the estimated value falls within a normal distribution for each node. This approach is a promising method for evaluating deterministic estimates and enhancing their reliability regarding application in electrical grids.

KEYWORDS

Distribution System State Estimation – Neural Networks – Explainability – Power Flow – Electrical Power Grids – Machine Learning

INTRODUCTION

Recently many works have been published that utilize artificial neural networks (ANN) for distribution system state estimation (DSSE) tasks in electrical power systems. Either sparse phasor measurement units (PMU) are used to feed an ANN with actual measurements like in [1], or the state estimation (SE) is conducted on basis of ANN generated measurement data like in the work [2]. Also physically inspired ANN estimators have been published. The authors in [3] integrate the connectivity information of the electrical network into the ANN's neuronal connections, while other sources leverage the valuable physical information of line parameters in a graph neural network [4]. As we have presented in [5], ANNs outperform conventional methods regarding computational performance and sparsity of measurement equipment in complex distribution grids. However, the results of ANN based state estimations are never fully compliant with physical laws. Uncertainties arise as ANNs are trained on data and patterns. Overfitting or poor training data can lead to inaccurate predictions or physically inconsistent results.

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A review in [6] underscores the crucial importance of using accurate datasets and the choice of hyperparameters. Besides these points, the quality of the predictions in relation to the available data is emphasized in [7] as well.

An approach to post-process ANN predictions for DSSE with a Gauss-Newton algorithm (GN) addresses this problem in [8]. The GN introduces physical laws to improve the precision of estimations. However, this does not ensure the result's consistency, as the results from the ANN are used as initialization for the GN. The input from the ANN could still be erroneous, which would lead to a false sense of security.

Furthermore, methods to evaluate generalization performance of trained ANNs have been developed from a statistical perspective. Works like [9] and [10] provide probabilistic error bounds for estimations, but this still does not ensure physical accordance of individual ANN outputs.

The doubts in ANN based SE reduce the spectrum of potential applications. E.g., decisions for system stability measures should be done on physically reliable foundation.

Therefore, this paper presents a method that applies physical laws to estimated nodal voltage phasors for the CIGRE LV grid as described in [11]. The balanced fundamental frequency results from the test set in our work in [5] were used for the presented experiments. The goal of this method is to identify impossible grid states and, in particular, to find unreasonable individual nodal results.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The deterministic nature of ANNs enables them to learn physics-based states of an electrical system from, e.g., simulation data. However, even with the decent generalization ability of trained ANNs on unknown test datasets, the SE results might not always be in accordance with physical laws. Furthermore, the results still need be considered free variables. Therefore, the measured dimensions remain the most reliable data source. To incorporate physical logic, nodal voltage and system impedances can be used alongside Kirchhoff's laws. The following section outlines how multiple possible combinations of grid states can be calculated from the SE results. In the next step, clustering is introduced to reduce the large amount of possible source and load states to the most relevant ones. These states then serve as input variables for a mesh current analysis. By using different measures of distance from the physically correct states to the ANN SE result, we obtain a best fit and nodal data distribution. The experiments are conducted for the distribution grid depicted in

Figure 1.

Computing Virtual Drains and Sources

Essentially, line currents I_{ij} can be computed from the system's bus impedance matrix, as demonstrated by the following equation.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^K \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} = I_{ij} \quad \text{with } i, j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. The benchmark grid with 15 loads, three photovoltaic generators, two voltage levels, and one slack (node 0).

Here, $\hat{V}_{i,0}$ and $\hat{V}_{j,0}$ are the estimated nodal voltages for K nodes along segments of lines (or transformers) with the complex bus impedance $jX_{i,j} + R_{i,j}$. Neglecting line capacitances, virtual load impedances $\underline{Z}_{i,j}^K$ may be calculated by equation (2) at node K .

$$\sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^K \frac{\hat{V}_{K0}}{I_{ij}} = \underline{Z}_{ij}^K \quad \text{with } i, j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 shows an example of an electrical network path with $K=4$. The load \underline{Z}_L is supplied via three π -equivalent lines. In this case, five potential load currents can be calculated from four nodal voltages. The number of possible combinations C_K is can be formulated as follows.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{K-1} (K - n) = C_K \quad (3)$$

Figure 2. Example branch within an electrical power system with four nodes, three lines, and one load.

In cases where a load is not located at the end of a branch, the method is extended by Kirchhoff's current law. Again currents through lines can be calculated as mentioned above. However, these possible line currents need to be distinguished based on whether they flow into or from the node of interest. Depending on the active power flow from or to a PV system, it is considered load or source state. The general formulation for a load current I_L at node K between two lines is depicted in equation (4).

$$\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^M \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} = I_L^K \quad \text{with } i, j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4)$$

Here, M represents the nodal voltages along a path, which can be used to calculate the currents that flow to node K . N stands for the number of nodes, which are located along the path after this node, respectively. The number of possible combinations is depicted by equation (5).

$$\sum_{n=1}^{M-1} (M - n) \times \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} (N - n) = C_K \quad (5)$$

In case a load is connected to node K , equation (3) can be used to calculate the virtual impedance. This concept, however, is also used to calculate PV system's injections. Figure 3 shows the described setting with a PV source instead. Here, the same method can be applied to calculate the possible current injection I_{PV} .

Figure 3. Example branch within electrical power system with decentralized generation at node 3.

To fully calculate single grid states, slack voltage sources need to be calculated as well. Assuming a short circuit impedance allows the calculation of the slack source voltage phasor \underline{V}_0 . The aforementioned Kirchhoff-based methods yield the source current \underline{I}_0 at the connection points. In equation (6), combinations of nodal voltages along the paths M, N, and L yield possible results for the source current.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^M \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} + \sum_{i=1}^{L-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^L \frac{\hat{V}_{i0} - \hat{V}_{j0}}{jX_{ij} + R_{ij}} = \underline{I}_0 \quad (6)$$

with $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$

In this setting, the following equation describes the amount of possible combinations of slack phasor states C_0 .

$$\sum_{n=1}^{M-1} (M - n) \times \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} (N - n) \times \sum_{n=1}^{L-1} (L - n) = C_K \quad (7)$$

Figure 4 shows a single line diagram with node 1 connected to a slack. Kirchhoff' current law yields the source current from predicted nodal voltages.

Figure 4. Slack source connected to node 1, with three connected paths within an electrical power system.

The following restrictions should be mentioned:

- I. In general, a “path” starts at the node where a virtual load or source has to be estimated and ends at either a node with more than two connections, another source, or another load.
- II. For the current objective of fundamental frequency power flow estimation, line capacitances are neglected when calculating the line currents.
- III. Decentralized generation is assumed to act as ideal current sources.
- IV. If the real part of a virtual load impedance is negative, the state is discarded and not considered physically relevant.

Clustering of Potential System States

As already shown in equations (3), (5), and (7), a large number of combinations can occur for a single system state. Table 1 shows the maximum number of possible combinations. To reduce computational effort, a clustering method is applied to group data by the most common values per component state. The maximum of clustered states per device is set to 10. The Density Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) algorithm is used for clustering, as it can deal with unknown arbitrary shaped data [12]. Since it can handle unknown

arbitrary-shaped data, it suits the challenge of grouping complex voltage phasors across the benchmark grid.

The clustering yields the most representative value per cluster. All combinations of these representative values are used to compute a first set of solutions. Then, the best fit of all condensed possibilities is determined. Then in a second step, all combinations from the best clusters are used to find the best fit within these groupings.

Table 1 Possible States for grid components in the benchmark grid

Node	Type	Path lengths			Combinations
		M	N	L	
2	Load	3	3	-	9
12	Load	2	-	-	1
16	Load	5	-	-	10
17	Load	2	-	-	1
18	Load	2	-	-	1
19	Load	3	-	-	3
22	Load	4	-	-	6
24	Load	3	3	-	9
35	Load/ PV	2	-	-	1
36	Load	2	-	-	1
37	Load	2	-	-	1
40	Load	2	-	-	1
41	Load	3	-	-	3
42	Load	2	-	-	1
43	Load	2	-	-	1
9	PV	3	2	-	3
32	PV	2	2	-	1
0	Slack	3	4	3	54
				Total	7,085,880

Distance and Error Measures

To observe differences in the way the best fitting physical state is found, the deviations from the estimated state are calculated by different measures. Additionally, the objective parameters are varied. One test is carried out by seeking the best fit for all nodal voltages, and another test is performed using only the nodal voltages of the PMU locations.

Error Measures

For observing the SE results and validating states against the ground truth, the mean absolute error (MAE) is chosen. As the MAE is a very natural measure, in this work it is used to evaluate deviations for entire grid states in phasor magnitudes and angles [13]. It is defined as follows.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i - \hat{Y}_i| \quad (8)$$

It describes the average error of the estimates \hat{Y} over n samples compared with the ground truth data Y .

Similarity Measures

As the MAE (when used as similarity measure: δ_{MAE}) might not be the best measure to minimize the distance between the SE results and the validation states, other measures are tested as well. When this method is applied to real measurements, the ground truth is unknown, therefore the choice of distance measure is making the choice of distance measure crucial. In this context, instead of evaluating magnitude and phase, the Cartesian representation of voltage phasors is evaluated.

The mean squared error (δ_{MSE}) is another measure of deviation. Compared to the MAE, it is more sensitive to single outliers due to the quadratic weighting the differences between \hat{Y} and Y over n samples.

$$\delta_{MSE}(Y, \hat{Y}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \quad (9)$$

As the Euclidean distance (δ_{ED}) is also a measure for multidimensional distances, it is tested for its suitability with multiple complex voltages within a single system state. It is defined as shown in equation (10).

$$\delta_{ED}(Y, \hat{Y}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2} \quad (10)$$

The Hausdorff distance (δ_{HD}) is typically used to evaluate dissimilarities in point sets and image segmentations. As the δ_{HD} is a max-min distance, it takes into account every point in the data. Therefore, spatial properties of the dataset are considered, not just every single distance of each pair of points. The directed δ_{HD} ($\check{\delta}_{HD}$) for n samples can be described as follows.

$$\check{\delta}_{HD}(Y, \hat{Y}) = \max\{\sum_{i=1}^n \min\{\sum_{j=1}^n \|Y_i - \hat{Y}_j\|\}\} \quad (11)$$

As the $\check{\delta}_{HD}$ is not symmetric ($\check{\delta}_{HD}(Y, \hat{Y}) \neq \check{\delta}_{HD}(\hat{Y}, Y)$), the δ_{HD} is computed as depicted in equation (12).

$$\delta_{HD}(Y, \hat{Y}) = \max\{\check{\delta}_{HD}(Y, \hat{Y}), \check{\delta}_{HD}(\hat{Y}, Y)\} \quad (12)$$

It is assumed that δ_{HD} is a potential measure for identifying similarities over all nodal phasors within a single system state at once. In this work, the algorithm from [14] is used, and the distance measure $\|Y_i - \hat{Y}_j\|$ is the δ_{ED} .

Figure 5. The validation process in two steps.

Validation Process

Figure 5 provides an overview of the steps presented above. Starting with the definition of possible component states, all possible combinations are clustered. The representative combinations of the clustered groups are then used to calculate a system snapshot with knowledge of grid impedances and the method of mesh current analysis. This fundamental method benefits from the ability to use ideal current sources (PV) while the system is supplied by voltage sources. For every solution, the deviations δ_{MAE} , δ_{MSE} , δ_{ED} , and δ_{HD} to the SE result are computed. By choosing one of these distance measures, the best fit can be identified. Based on this best fit, the related clusters of component states are used for more specific calculations. Again the best fit within these groups is identified, and the distribution of possible phasors (magnitude and phase) per node can be investigated. This includes the clustered results and the results from the best fit clusters.

Considering the later application in real grids, two methods of distance analysis are tested. One experiment is conducted for the distances of all nodal voltages of an SE result to the same nodal voltages within the validation results ("fit all"). Another test evaluates the distance of the measured voltage phasors at nodes 6, 22, and 28 ("fit to measurements").

For this work, a test set from our ANN harmonic SE from [15] is used. It consists of 3,253 system states (ANN predictions and ground truth data) for 20 harmonic orders. For this work, the fundamental order data is used.

RESULTS

In the following sections, the findings of the presented methodology are outlined in the following order. Firstly, the distance metrics for validation states are compared based on the ground truth data. Then, the best metric is evaluated regarding its correlations with the ANN predictions. In the final sections, examples of states that could be considered "valid" or "invalid" are presented. They are identified based on the best metric. Firstly, the entire grid states are depicted, followed by visualizations of the range of physically possible grid states per node. These evaluations focus on the error in magnitude, as it is considered more important for DSSE applications.

Figure 6. Cumulative distribution functions of the best fits' mean absolute error against ground truth.

- a) All distance metrics "fit all" b) All distance measures "fit to measurement" c) "fit all" vs. "fit to measurement" mean squared error d) "fit all" vs. "fit to measurement" Hausdorff

Performance of Similarity Measures

To evaluate the effectiveness of different similarity measures in matching physically solved states with the predicted phasors, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) is chosen to compare the measures against each other. It is also used to compare the methods "fit all" and "fit to measurement".

Figure 6 shows the CDFs for the different metrics' MAEs over all states within the test data set. The steeper a curve is, the lower the error rate. Generally, all metrics yield quite similar results. Hence, sections have been zoomed in to identify the better measure. Comparing curves in Figure 6 a), the usage of δ_{ED} or δ_{MSE} appears to find the best fits compared to ground truth when all phasors in the grid are compared. δ_{HD} shows worse performance. The same behaviour can be observed in graph b). Here, only measurement locations are used to identify the best fits. When directly comparing the δ_{MSE} results for "fit all" and "fit to measurement" in graph c), the "fit all" method features a slightly better performance. This only changes if the δ_{HD} is used as the metric. Here, it appears this measure is more suitable when only matching states with the actual measured phasors.

Figure 7. Comparison of mean absolute errors for prediction and different distance metrics. a) Error in magnitude. Low voltage magnitudes referenced to 20kV. b) Error in phase.

Precision of the Validation in Respect to Ground Truth

In order to compare prediction results and the best fits for the different validation metrics, box plots are used to show the range of MAEs in magnitude and phase. Figure 7 a) supports the findings from Figure 6, as the medians and first and second quartiles of δ_{MSE} and δ_{ED} are slightly lower than the markers for δ_{HD} and δ_{MAE} . However, this pattern only applies to the MAE in magnitude. Figure 7 b) shows the lower values for the median, first and second quartile for the δ_{MAE} . Outliers within the validation states (especially magnitude), are indicators for erroneous predictions, as the sections below will show in detail.

The exact values can be found in Table 2.

Table 2 Comparison of 1st to 3rd quartiles for mean absolute errors against ground truth.

	Prediction		MSE/ED		HD		MAE	
	Mag. [V]	Phase [°]	Mag. [V]	Phase [°]	Mag. [V]	Phase [°]	Mag. [V]	Phase [°]
1 st Quartile	5.35	0.013	13.15	0.04	14.58	0.0397	13.26	0.038
Median	7.33	0.019	22.96	0.068	26.6	0.0687	23.41	0.065
3 rd Quartile	10.76	0.027	41.17	0.115	44.48	0.1192	41.15	0.111

When observing the MAE results for δ_{MSE} over the ordered prediction MAE in Figure 8, only a slight correlation between the validation best fit MAE and the SE error can be observed. However, as the SE error increases, the best fit states more frequently exceed the SE precision. In total, the magnitude estimation of 119 states improved due to the validation method. The phase estimation of 94 states improved as well. In field tests, the true value would not be available to compare this measure, but it already provides an indication of the physical correctness of the validation strategy.

Figure 8. Mean absolute errors of prediction (ordered) and best similarity measure (Mean squared error). a) Magnitude b) Phase

Identification of Invalid States

From this point onward, only the δ_{MSE} will be considered the relevant metric. The distance between physically correct states and the prediction is used to rank the quality of the prediction.

The following Figure 9 shows one of the top five shortest distances and Figure 10 shows one of the five largest distances. Observing the per-unit (p.u.) error in magnitude for Figure 9, the error is below 0.09% for all nodes. This state is considered “valid”.

Figure 9. Magnitudes across all nodes within the electrical grid and the deviation to the best fit (Mean squared error distance). State assumed to be "valid".

Figure 10. Magnitudes across all nodes within the electrical grid and the deviation to the best fit (Mean squared error distance). State assumed to be "invalid". Inconsistent estimation at node 2.

However, Figure 10 depicts a state with a low similarity to the physical representation. The error in one low voltage branch is large for all nodes (>20%). This can be explained, as the first node's state in this branch (node 2) cannot be determined correctly. All predicted phasors in direction of the slack (Nodes 0, 1) feature a larger phase angle (0.115° , 0.156° vs 0.0673°), which is impossible in case of positive power flow. Also, the magnitude states around node 2 are not reasonable (Nodes 2: 0.9965 p.u., 3: 0.9966 p.u., 4: 0.9966 p.u.). As this yields only negative or small virtual impedances ($P_{3ph} \approx 7.2$ MW, $Q_{3ph} \approx -3.08$ MVar), the mesh analysis indicates a voltage rise of 0.2 p.u. for the entire branch.

Figure 11. Normal distributions of physically possible magnitudes per node and classification of Best fit and prediction for a "valid state"

Figure 12. Normal distributions of physically possible magnitudes per node and classification of Best fit and prediction for an “invalid state”

Classification of Nodal Results

To show the range of possible physical states for a consistent estimation from Figure 9 and an erroneous state from Figure 10, Figure 11 Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. and Figure 12 present the detailed results for these states. In Figure 11, the predicted and the best fit magnitudes are especially close to each other and are around the mean value of all validation results. For every node, the predicted values fall inside the 1σ interval of the normal distribution of computed states.

When observing the invalid state in Figure 12, aside from the problematic low-voltage branch from Figure 10, the predicted magnitudes fall into improbable regions of the nodal distributions. In general, the base voltage of the state is increased by the large capacitive current from the virtual load located at node 2.

DISCUSSION

The proposed method enables the classification of deterministic voltage phasor predictions from ANNs for power grids. The method focuses on distribution grids with low measurement coverage in complex grid topologies. In detail, the following key findings contribute to the field of ANN-based DSSE.

Key Findings

Even if an ANN exhibits a high degree of generalization and provides very precise estimations, inconsistencies can occur, which the proposed method can identify. However, the best-fitted results do not necessarily improve the state estimation. Only about 3% of the best fits achieve

a better MAE compared to the prediction. The best fit and all other computed combinations can offer insight into the range of possibilities, ensuring that the state is physically logical. As a mean error metric is used to evaluate the quality of prediction, the error in the prediction compared to the ground truth can be smaller than the best fit's MAE. Yet, the prediction could still contain physical inconsistencies, identified by the physics-aware validation.

Another outcome of this work is the unsuitability of the δ_{HD} as a multidimensional measure for complex grid states. The δ_{HD} improved the accuracy of the validation states when applied to only three nodal measurements and not the entire grid state.

This leads to the finding of no major differences in the choice of distance measures. It seems suitable to compute the similarity of the entire grid state instead of just the readings from PMUs. However, this could change if the algorithm is applied to real grid measurements and field predictions. Interestingly, the δ_{ED} and δ_{MSE} metrics always identified the same states as the best fit, even though one is the geometric mean and the other is the arithmetic mean.

Regarding measurement placement, it could be beneficial to place a PMU at the slack node, as the precision of the proposed method heavily depends on the slack's phasor. Due to the application of mesh analysis, it is the dominant parameter for achieving good precision in phase information.

Potential Improvements and Limitations

The current method to identify invalid states can be optimized. Only outliers outside the fourth quartile of distances to the 3,253 best fits were considered invalid; however, smaller inconsistencies could also be relevant. A rule needs to be found to transform the binary valid/invalid classification into more dynamic information. The approach of using probability distributions per node could address this challenge, such as setting limits based on multiples of standard deviations.

Another aspect regarding the MAE as the error metric, is its questionable suitability for different applications. In the context of machine learning, the MAE is a typical measure, but if a higher resolution of single errors per node is required, other measures might be necessary.

Referring to Table 1, the variance of single loads (e.g., nodes 12, 17, 18) lacks variance due to restriction I. Compared to the load at node 23, these loads would show higher variance if the method for these loads were extended by Kirchhoff's current law. This enhancement would allow potential currents from other branches to be considered for the virtual loads as well.

CONCLUSION

A novel method for DSSE validation has been developed. The major benefit of this method is its ability to evaluate deterministic ANN predictions, which are based on only a few PMU measurement locations, and to identify uncertainties in the predicted grid states. It is also capable of identifying single problematic nodal voltages. However, further research needs to be conducted on the severity of the inconsistencies.

Finally, some future perspectives and necessary improvements should be mentioned. A significant achievement would be the application of this method in real field or laboratory SE. This could lead to the generation of penalties or rewards to enable reinforcement learning.

There are major challenges that need to be addressed before this is possible. Most importantly, the strategy for clearly identifying valid and invalid states has to be quantified. In this work, only large outliers of the distance metric are considered as invalid states.

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NOMENCLATURE

Symbols

δ	Distance/ Similarity
σ	Standard deviation
ANN	Artificial neural network
C	Number of possible combinations
C'	Line's capacitance per length
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
DBSCAN	Density based spatial clustering of applications with noise
DSSE	Distribution system state estimation
I	Current given in Ampère
K	Node of interest or within a single network branch the number of nodes
L	Number of nodes after a load/drain or the third branch's number of nodes
M	Number of nodes before a load/drain or the first branch's number of nodes
MAE	Mean absolute error
MSE	Mean squared error
N	Number of nodes after a load/drain or the second branch's number of nodes
P	Active power
PMU	Phasor measurement unit
p.u.	Dimensions in per unit
PV	Photovoltaic system
Q	Reactive power
R'	Line's resistance per length
SE	State estimation
V	Voltage given in volts
X'	Line's reactance per length
Y	An vector or multidimensional matrix of data
Z	Impedance

Subscripts/ Superscripts

\wedge	Indicates an estimated quantity
3ph	The variable describes the total sum of 3 phases
ED	Euclidean distance
HD	Hausdorff distance
L	Marks a load
l	Marks a cable parameter

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